

Temporal trend of Parkinson's disease mortality between 2009 and 2023 in the municipality of Uberlândia (Minas Gerais, Brazil)

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Abstract— The aim of this study was to analyse the temporal trend of deaths associated with and due to Parkinson's disease (PD) among residents of Uberlândia (Minas Gerais, Brazil). For this purpose, an ecological, time-series study was conducted using death certificates from adults residents with PD who died in Uberlândia between 2009 and 2023. For both overall and sex-specific mortality rates, temporal trends were analysed using joinpoint regressions, estimating the annual percent change in rates. Between 2009 and 2023, a significant average increase in PD-related mortality rates was observed. Overall mortality due to PD showed an upward trend of 6.64% per year, while rates with the disease as an associated cause fluctuated over the years, exhibiting alternating periods of increase and decrease. For both sexes, PD-related mortality has increased over time. However, the burden of PD is growing more rapidly among men, with a statistically significant annual increase of 7.91% in deaths due to other causes and 8.23% in deaths due to PD. Therefore, Uberlândia has been facing challenges in managing PD.

Keywords — Parkinson's disease, mortality, epidemiological surveillance, temporal trend, joinpoint regression.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Brazil, Parkinson's disease (PD) has been responsible for several deaths annually, gradually emerging as a significant public health concern. In two decades, mortality due to PD among individuals aged 60 years or older nearly doubled in the country, increasing from 8.1 deaths per 10,000 inhabitants in 2002 to 15.4 deaths per 10,000 inhabitants in 2021 [1].

However, this rise in mortality due to PD has not been restricted to the national level, but has also been evident in both all Brazilian macro-regions [1] and their respective state capitals [2]. The increase in different regions of the country suggests that the burden of the disease transcends regional disparities and levels of urbanization, affecting both more developed urban centres and less-resourced areas alike.

This highlights the important role of local-level studies in understanding the epidemiological profile of the disease under the influence of local conditions, while also reflecting the quality of life of the local population. Furthermore, as equity and decentralization are core principles of the universal public health system in Brazil (Unified Health System) [3, 4], it is essential to understand local mortality trends to effectively guide and adapt public health policies.

However, studies focusing on PD-related mortality at the municipal level in Brazil remain scarce, preventing targeted public health responses. In this context, the aim of this study was to analyse the temporal trend of deaths associated with and due to Parkinson's disease among residents of the municipality of Uberlândia (Minas Gerais, Brazil) in the period from 2009 to 2023.

By providing evidence on the evolution of deaths on a municipal scale, this study highlights the burden of the disease faced by Uberlândia in recent years, presenting the first local evidence of the disease trends in Brazil. More importantly, the findings of this study can contribute directly to the formulation of strategies to better manage Parkinson's disease in Uberlândia.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study design

This is an ecological, time-series study on PD-related deaths among adults residing in Uberlândia, Minas Gerais, Brazil, between 2009 and 2023.

B. Mortality estimates

Annual mortality data, disaggregated by sex, age, place of residence, year of death and causes of death, were obtained from the Mortality Information System of the Brazilian Ministry of Health. All deaths that occurred among adult

residents of Uberlândia with PD who died between 2009 and 2023 were considered. Thus, only those death certificates that listed the *G20* code, which corresponds to the disease in the 10th revision of the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, as the primary or secondary cause of death, were included.

For the temporal trend analysis, the age- and sex-adjusted mortality rates for specific causes of death (i.e., PD as the main cause of death) and multiple causes of death (i.e., PD as a secondary cause of death) were estimated for each year. In addition to the overall rates, sex-specific rates were also estimated, i.e., age-adjusted mortality rates were estimated separately for males and females.

In both estimates, the adjustment was performed using the direct method, based on the population reported in the 2022 Brazilian Census. Thus, annual mortality rates were first calculated for each group by dividing the annual number of deaths by the corresponding population estimates provided by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics. Then, these specific rates were weighted by the proportion of the standard population in each group to obtain the adjusted rate, expressed per 100,000 inhabitants.

Therefore, the adjustment considered differences in age distribution and sex ratio for the overall estimate, while the sex-specific estimate took into account differences in age distribution between men and women. For these estimates, it was verified that all death certificates contained data on the sex and age of the individual at the time of death, and it was not necessary to exclude any death certificates.

All data processing and rate estimates were performed using *R* (version 4.5.0).

C. Statistical analysis

The Chi-squared test was employed to assess whether the proportion of PD-related deaths differed significantly between males and females. In addition, the Fisher's exact test was used to assess whether the distribution of age groups differed significantly between males and females who died from the disease or another cause of death. In both tests, a significance level of 5% was considered and analyses were performed using the *R* language.

In addition, analyses of temporal trends in overall and sex-specific mortality rates, stratified by cause of death, were performed using joinpoint regressions. In each model, the natural logarithm of mortality rates was modelled as a linear function of the year of death, with log-transformed rates as the dependent variable and year as the independent variable.

This modelling approach provides a better representation of temporal trends in mortality rates. This is because it accounts for changes that may occur at different points in time rather than assuming a constant trend over the entire study period.

When a statistically significant change in the trend is identified, the rates is modelled using multiple linear segments, each corresponding to a distinct time interval with a different slope and connected by inflexion points (i.e., joinpoints). Thus, it is possible to identify periods of increase,

decrease, or stabilization in rates.

For both global and specific rates, up to four joinpoints were considered, testing whether more joinpoints significantly improve the fit. The model selection was based on the weighted Bayesian information criterion, which balances the quality of the fit and the complexity of the model, penalizing overly complex models to avoid over-fitting. Thus, the final model selected was the one with the lowest metric.

The trends were expressed as the annual percentage change (APC) for each identified segment, with the respective 95% confidence intervals (CI). Thus, a positive APC indicated an increasing trend, a negative APC reflected a decreasing trend, and an APC close to zero suggested that the rate has remained stable over time. In addition, to summarize the trends when more than one slope was identified, the average annual percentage change (AAPC) and its corresponding CI were estimated over the full period.

The analyses of temporal trends were performed with the Joinpoint Regression Program (version 5.4.0).

D. Ethical considerations

This study involved the analysis of the Brazilian open data, which is available in the public domain, obviating the need for ethical approval.

III. RESULTS

Between 2009 and 2023, Uberlândia recorded the highest number of PD-related deaths among residents within the Triângulo Mineiro region. Among all the municipalities in Minas Gerais, it was the third, alongside the municipality of Contagem, with the highest number of deaths of residents with the disease, accounting for 2.72% of all registered deaths of individuals with PD in the state.

In Uberlândia, 367 adult residents with the disease died between 2009 and 2023, which corresponded to approximately 0.61% of all deaths of residents registered in the municipality. Of this total, 168 deaths (45.78%) were attributed to PD and 199 (54.22%) were due to other underlying causes of death (i.e., PD was listed as a secondary cause on the death certificate).

Deaths were more frequent among men, who comprised 55.03% of deaths due to PD and 57.29% of those where PD was a secondary cause. Among deaths due to PD, the sex ratio did not differ significantly from the expected proportions ($\chi^2 = 1.929$, $p = 0.165$), suggesting a balanced number of deaths between men and women. Conversely, among deaths from other causes, the sex ratio differed significantly ($\chi^2 = 4.226$, $p = 0.040$), indicating a disproportionate representation between sex.

Men also experienced mortality at younger ages compared to women. Deaths among women occurred after age 60, while earlier deaths were observed exclusively in men (3.38% of men died before age 60), especially among those who died due to the disease. However, age distribution did not differ significantly by sex, whether death was due to the disease

Fig. 1. Temporal trends in sex- and age-adjusted mortality rates (per 100,000 inhabitants) of residents with Parkinson's disease in the municipality of Uberlândia (Minas Gerais) between 2009 and 2023. Mortality rates are presented stratified by cause of death, i.e., deaths of residents caused by Parkinson's disease (Parkinson's disease as a primary cause) and deaths caused by other causes of residents with the disease (Parkinson's disease as a secondary cause). For cause of death, the segments represent periods identified by the joinpoint regression model, with each segment showing the estimated annual percentage change (APC). Changes in the slope indicate statistically significant trend shifts over time, and are represented by an asterisk.

(Fisher's exact test, $p = 0.43$) or another cause (Fisher's exact test, $p = 0.51$).

Among residents with PD who died from another cause, the main causes of death varied between years and specific differences by sex were observed. In general, Alzheimer's disease (10.59% of female deaths and 9.65% of male deaths) and immobility syndrome (paraplegic) (8.24% of female deaths and 10.53% of male deaths) were the leading causes of death in the period among those with PD who died from another cause.

In addition to these causes, several conditions appeared frequently as main causes of death. Among these, various diseases of the circulatory system, which together accounted for 23.70% of male deaths and 28.27% of female deaths. COVID-19 was also an important cause of death, accounting for more fatalities among men than among women (5.88% of female deaths and 7.02% of male deaths).

Nineteen diseases were the leading causes of death for both sexes, representing 64.82% of fatalities, while an additional 25 were exclusive to women and 32 to men. These diseases, observed in only one of the sexes, were generally responsible for no more than two deaths—except for malignant neoplasm of the prostate, which has been a common cause of death among men (6.14%), especially since 2017.

A. Overall temporal trends in Parkinson's disease mortality

The absolute number of deaths among residents with PD has been increased annually, with at least ten deaths reported each year in Uberlândia. In the past three years alone, more than 140 people with the disease have died in the municipality, with at least 43 deaths reported each year.

Mortality due to PD has also been increasing over the

last 15 years in Uberlândia, from 1.65 deaths per 100,000 inhabitants in 2009 to 2.64 deaths per 100,000 inhabitants in 2023. Despite some fluctuations in rates during the period, mortality due to the disease showed a statistically significant upward trend without the presence of inflection points, with a growth rate of approximately 6.64% ($CI = [2.39\%, 13.25\%]$) per year (Figure 1).

Unlike mortality due to PD, mortality from other causes among residents with PD showed a trend with several significant inflection points over time (Figure 1). Between 2009 and 2023, mortality rates associated with PD alternated between periods of growth and decline, with APC values significantly greater than those observed for mortality attributed to the disease.

In the first six years, there was an increase in mortality of 14.96% ($CI = [9.87\%, 27.62\%]$) per year. However, from 2014 to 2017, it decreased at a similar rate to the prior increase ($APC = -14.62\%$, $CI = [-20.88\%, -4.01\%]$). Between 2017 and 2021, the trend reversed, showing a significant increase of 32.54% per year ($CI = [26.76\%, 45.43\%]$). From 2021 onwards, rates decreased again ($APC = -17.76\%$, $CI = [-26.49\%, -7.72\%]$).

Despite the alternation between periods of increasing and decreasing mortality rates associated with PD, the AAPC for the entire period was 7.09% ($CI = [5.56\%, 9.70\%]$), reflecting an overall upward trend over the period.

B. Sex-specific temporal trends in Parkinson's disease mortality

Among men, a significant positive APC was observed in both disease-caused ($APC = 8.23\%$, $CI = [1.58\%, 20.30\%]$) and disease-associated ($APC = 7.91\%$, $CI = [2.72\%, 16.47\%]$) mortality, indicating an upward trend in deaths (Figure 2). Although an increasing trend

Fig. 2. Sex-specific temporal trends in age-adjusted mortality rates (per 100,000 inhabitants) of residents with Parkinson's disease in the municipality of Uberlândia (Minas Gerais) between 2009 and 2023. Sex-specific mortality rates are presented stratified by cause of death, i.e., deaths of residents caused by Parkinson's disease (Parkinson's disease as a primary cause) and deaths caused by other causes of residents with the disease (Parkinson's disease as a secondary cause). For cause of death and each sex, the segments represent periods identified by the joinpoint regression model, with each segment showing the estimated annual percentage change (APC). Changes in the slope indicate statistically significant trend shifts over time, and are represented by an asterisk.

in mortality was observed among women (Figure 2), the APC was not statistically significant, whether PD was the underlying cause (APC = 1.15%, $CI = [-4.78\%, 9.35\%]$) or an associated cause (APC = 6.06%, $CI = [-0.49\%, 16.21\%]$).

IV. DISCUSSION

This study reports the temporal trend of mortality among residents with PD in Uberlândia (Minas Gerais, Brazil) between 2009 and 2023, marking the first effort to characterize mortality trends from this disease at the municipal level in the country. In practice, this characterisation of temporal trends is important in order to understand the impact of local conditions on PD mortality, and thus subsidise the adoption of health strategies in the municipality to better meet the current needs of residents.

A. Overall temporal trends in Parkinson's disease mortality

The findings of this study indicated an upward trend in overall PD mortality between 2009 and 2023 in Uberlândia, mirroring the trend observed in the Southeast macro-region between 2002 and 2021 [1], but with a more marked increase. The annual upward trend of 6.64% in sex- and age-adjusted mortality rates therefore suggests an increasing burden of Parkinson's disease at the municipal level over the years.

This study also demonstrated that the overall mortality associated with the disease was more variable, with fluctuations over time marked by alternating periods of both increases and decreases in sex- and age-adjusted mortality rates. This suggests that over time, there have been significant changes in mortality trends associated with the disease, possibly due to transformations in the epidemiological and care scenario in Uberlândia.

The adoption of health strategies to combat specific diseases in the municipality at different times may be one of the factors responsible for modulating this pattern. Furthermore, although Alzheimer's disease and immobility syndrome are frequent annual causes of death among residents with the disease, this oscillating pattern may also be reflecting, to a greater or lesser extent, the presence of different co-morbidities and diseases, as death causes, among residents with PD over the periods.

This hypothesis is partly because the number of distinct diseases responsible for the deaths of residents with PD declined from 2009-2014 to 2014-2017, suggesting a possible improved management of certain conditions in Uberlândia. It was observed that deaths from Chagas disease were concentrated between 2009 and 2014, possibly reflecting improved local zoonosis control in consecutive years—a broader public health goal in Minas Gerais in recent decades [5].

However, this pattern reversed from 2017 onwards, with a rise in the diversity of causes of death, surpassing the initial period. Especially since 2020, there has been an increase in mortality from all causes, reflecting the challenges faced by the local health system in managing other health conditions alongside COVID-19. In 2023, COVID-19 was no longer a cause of death among residents with the disease, accompanied by a decline in deaths from some infections and neoplasms, which were specifically concentrated between 2018 and 2022.

Despite the absolute increase in the number of deaths from 2022 to 2023, the trend indicated a decline in the sex- and age-adjusted mortality rates associated with the disease between 2021 and 2023. This downward trend may be reflecting the significant peak (identified as an inflection point) in mortality due to other causes among residents with PD during 2021—a pattern also observed for other causes of death in the municipality during the same year, as reported in the 28th Health Surveillance Bulletin of Uberlândia [6].

Despite short-term variations in disease-related mortality rates, the positive AAPC (7.09%) over the period highlights an average increase in disease-related mortality and therefore a consistent long-term increase in disease-related burden at the municipal level. This underscores the importance of adopting a multidisciplinary approach to the management of Parkinson's disease, taking into account not only the condition itself but also the presence of co-morbidities and associated diseases that require ongoing monitoring and targeted interventions.

The fact that Alzheimer's disease and immobility syndrome alone were the two main causes of death in both men and women reflects the complexity of the health profile of some residents with PD before death and further underlines the importance of viewing Parkinson's disease through a multidisciplinary, continuous care lens. On the one hand, death due to Alzheimer's disease suggests that residents had substantially impaired cognitive function, indicating a co-occurrence of PD and Alzheimer's disease.

Although PD is best known for mainly affecting movements and, more generally, motor function, some patients end up developing cognitive decline over the course of the disease [7]. Mild cognitive impairment is thought to be present in some patients from the early stages of the disease, and may progress to dementia in more advanced stages [8].

On the other hand, death due to the immobility syndrome suggests that Parkinson's disease in some residents is progressing to a critical clinical stage before death, in which the individual has considerable limitations in voluntary movements, the symptoms are extremely severe and the individual is usually bedridden for a long time and in need of daily support from caregivers or family members for hygiene and basic needs [9].

Deaths from these two causes may therefore serve as a warning on multiple challenges faced by the health system in Uberlândia in managing PD. Firstly, it points to possible gaps in promoting physical activity and providing functional physiotherapy to individuals with PD. Second, it suggests potential deficiencies in the early identification of functional or cognitive decline among residents with advanced PD, as well as reinforcing the need for more humanised care for those at the end of life.

Finally, it may point to systemic limitations in the ability of local health services to address the evolving needs of patients across the various stages of the disease. This is because, as the disease progresses, the marked motor and non-motor signs and symptoms of Parkinson's become more severe and medication-induced complications arise [10], requiring frequent adjustments to the medication therapy plan or the adoption of advanced therapies for the management of Parkinson's disease [11, 12].

Among advanced therapies for Parkinson's, deep brain stimulation is the only one available through Unified Health System in Brazil, which has been included as part of the National Health Agency's list of procedures since 2011. Since 2017, it has been an indicated procedure for the treatment of the disease under the Clinical Protocol and Therapeutic Guidelines for Parkinson's Disease, established by Joint Ordinance No. 10, on October 31, 2017 [13]. However,

access to this treatment remains unavailable in the public health system of Uberlândia. Even in the private health system, the procedure has only been offered since 2020 [14], indicating delays in the provision of treatment for advanced PD, even within the private healthcare system.

Combined with this, individuals with PD become more susceptible to various co-morbidities, the propensity for prolonged hospitalisation increases, and hospital admissions are more frequent [15]. Therefore, in addition to the lack of infrastructure and professionals specialising in movement disorders to carry out more advanced treatment, particularly in the public health system, which is often the primary source of care for the broader population, there may also be gaps in the provision of the multidisciplinary, continuously care needed by residents with the disease, involving collaboration between different health professionals, such as geriatricians, psychiatrists, physiotherapists, nurses, occupational therapists, nutritionists, among others.

B. Sex-specific temporal trends in Parkinson's disease mortality

In contrast to the prevailing belief that deaths in individuals with PD are more frequent among women [16], this study observed higher frequency and higher age-adjusted mortality rates among men with the disease, despite the fact that there was no significant difference between the sex ratios for deaths due to the disease. However, this finding corroborates the pattern observed at the national level [1]. This finding is particularly interesting, as Uberlândia has consistently had a predominantly female population since the year 2009, according to IBGE estimates.

One possible reason for the higher number of deaths among men with PD, especially as a result of other causes of death, may be that they proactively seek medical attention less often than women. In fact, this may be reflecting the phenomenon of men's low adherence to health services observed in Brazil, in which men tend to use health services, whether public or private health services, less until more acute or serious symptoms arise [17, 18].

In Brazil, many men still avoid seeking medical attention, often due to fear of having a serious disease and no longer being able to support the family, misinformation, or, above all, cultural stigma surrounding preventive care, especially when it is necessary to carry out medical procedure such as the digital rectal exam—an important exam to help detect issues in the prostate gland at an early stage, before more serious results arise [19]. Thus, all these factors also help to explain why prostate cancer has become the fourth leading cause of death among residents with PD, accounting for 6.14% of male deaths.

Although mortality rates due to and associated with the disease have remained stable among women with increasing but non-significant trends, this does not imply that the disease has no impact on this group. Especially because it is believed that there are specific differences between the sexes, with women being more likely to develop disabling motor complications and non-motor fluctuations [8]. Thus, even non-significant upward trends may carry meaningful

implications for health planning, as women will also require health care throughout the course of the disease and specific interventions may often be necessary.

V. CONCLUSION

In Uberlândia, mortality among residents with PD has been increasing over the years, highlighting the persistent public health burden posed by the disease since 2009. Although the ideal treatment for PD requires an integrated multidisciplinary approach, the management of motor and non-motor symptoms, rehabilitation, and palliative care provided within the municipality appear to be insufficient to promote well-being throughout the course of the disease, as well as to ensure a more humanised end of life. Therefore, the findings of this study may serve as a basis for public health decision-making and targeted social interventions, with the aim of enhancing healthcare provision and quality of life for people living with Parkinson's disease in Uberlândia. Future research may explore temporal trends in other municipalities to enhance the understanding of local health disparities in PD.

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